

THERMOMECHANICAL PROCESSING OF SUPERPLASTIC AlN PARTICULATE REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Thermomechanical processing to produce high strain rate superplasticity (HSRS) for 1N90 pure aluminium, AlN/1N90 and AlN/6061 Al composites fabricated by a P/M method were developed, and the relationship between HSRS of aluminium alone and the composites and the thermomechanical processing were investigated.

1N90 Al and AlN/1N90 Al composite have the fine grain of about $2\mu\text{m}$ after hot rolling and extrusion. The AlN/6061 Al composite with $V_f=0.30$ hot-rolled after extrusion exhibited the total elongation of 300-500% at the strain rate range 0.8S^{-1} and at 873K. Maximum volume fraction of AlN particle to produce HSRS in AlN/6061 Al composite was 0.4.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic whisker or particulate reinforced aluminium alloy composites have a great potential for automobile engineering components, aerospace structures, semi-conductor packaging etc, since these composites exhibit a high specific elastic modulus and specific tensile strength, excellent wear resistance and heat resistance, low thermal expansion and good dimensional stability.

High Strain rate Superplasticity (HSRS) is expected to establish an efficiently near-net shape forming for such ceramic whisker or particulate reinforced aluminium alloy composites(1-10, 12) .

An AlN particulate reinforced aluminium alloy composite exhibits a high elastic modulus and a high thermal conductivity(11), and their thermal expansion is similar to silicon so that the AlN particulate reinforced aluminium alloy composite is expected to apply to semi-conductor packaging in the aerospace structure. But, in order to establish HSRS for AlN and aluminium alloy system composites, it is necessary to make clear the relationship between HSRS for the composite and thermomechanical processing.

The purpose of this study is to develop the thermomechanical process to produce superplasticity at high strain rate(HSRS) for an AlN particulate reinforced pure aluminium and 6061 aluminium alloy composites, and also to make clear the deformation mechanism of HSRS.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Aluminium nitride particle (AlN₃) with an average particle sizes of 1.35 μm and AlN₂ with that of 1.78μm were used as reinforcement materials(Table1). The aluminium nitride AlN₃ was fabricated by a carbothermal nitridation and AlN₂ by a direct nitridation method. 1N90 pure aluminium and 6061 aluminium alloy powders with particle size under 45μm(Table2) were mixed with both AlN particles in an alcoholic solvent for 24 hours by a blender machine, respectively. Volume fractions of AlN particles used were 0.15, 0.30 and 0.40. These mixed powders were sintered at 773K in vacuum under the pressure of 200MPa for 20minutes. The as-hot pressed billet was reformed at 773K in air under the pressure of 495MPa for 20 minutes.

Table 1 Chemical compositions of AlN particles used as reinforcement material

materials	Fe	Si	Cu	Mg	Ni	Cr	O	N	C	Ca	d50
AlN ₂	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	wt%	wt%	wt%	---	μm
	69	102	5	14	5	6	1.29	32.9	0.03	---	1.78
AlN ₃	ppm	ppm					wt%	wt%	wt%		μm
	50	100					1	33.8	0.2		1.35

AlN₂:a direct nitridation , AlN₃:a carbothermal nitridation

Table 2 Chemical compositions of 6061 and 1N90 aluminium powder

Materials	Fe	Cu	Si	Zn	Mn	Mg	Ti	Cr	Ni	Al
6061	wt%	wt%	wt%		wt%	wt%		wt%		wt%
	0.27	0.25	0.74	-	0.07	1.08	--	0.13	---	97.46
1N90	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm		ppm	
	43	6	41	17	5	3	2	--	3	99.99

Thermomechanical processing used to produce superplasticity in the 1N90 Al and composites was hot rolled after extrusion. Hot extrusion was performed with the extrusion ratio of 44 at 773K. After heating in temperature range from 673K up to 923K, 1N90 Al and the composite was hot-rolled. The strain in each

rolling pass was less than 0.1 and the reheating-holding time between rolling passes was about 5 minutes. Final thicknesses of the composite hot-rolled were about 0.75mm. Tensile specimens with a 4mm gage width and a 5.5mm gage length were pulled at 848 and 873K for AlN3/6061, and 913K for 1N90 and AlN/1N90 Al composites in the strain rate range from 0.01 to about $2S^{-1}$. The microstructure and fracture surface were observed by TEM and SEM.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(1)SEM microstructures

Fig. 1 indicates TEM microstructures of 1N90 pure aluminium and AlN2/1N90 Al composite hot-rolled after extrusion. The grain size of 1N90 Al and AlN2/1N90 Al composite are about $2\mu m$. Therefore, hot rolling and extrusion has a good effect to build a fine grain in aluminium matrix. And AlN particles are dispersed homogeneously in the matrix even in the high volume fraction of 0.40.

Fig. 1 TEM microstructures of (a)1N90 pure aluminium and (b)AlN2/1N90 Al composite hot-rolled after extrusion

(1)Superplasticity of 1N90 pure aluminium

A flow stress(s) in superplastic materials can be related to the true strain rate($\dot{\epsilon}$) via the equation $s=K\dot{\epsilon}^m$, where K is a constant. The m value, which is obtained from the equation, $m=d(\log\sigma)/d(\log \dot{\epsilon})$, is the strain rate sensitivity of a flow stress. It is necessary for the m value to be larger than 0.3 for superplastic materials because a higher m value suppresses the development of necking and leads to higher total elongation.

Fig.2 (a) and (b) indicate effect of rolling temperature on superplastic characteristics of 1N90 pure aluminium extruded. Rolling temperatures used are 473, 723, 773 and 873K. Testing temperature is 913K which is below liquid temperature of pue aluminium. 1N90 pure aluminiums hot-rolled below 723K after extrusion show the m value less than 0.2, but the m value of the 1N90 Al becomes about 0.4 in the case of hot rolling at more than 773K. Therefore, 1N90 pure aluminium fabricated by P/M method and hot-rolled at 773-873K after extrusion could produce superplasticity.

The total elongation of 1N90 pure aluminium hot-rolled below 723K becomes less than 100%, but the pure aluminium hot-rolled at 773-873K exhibits the total elongation 100-300% in the strain rate range from 0.002 to $0.05s^{-1}$ and

at 913K. It is necessary to hot-roll the composite above the temperature at which the recrystallisation of pure aluminium occurs.

Fig.2(a) Effect of rolling temperature on flow stress of 1N90 pure aluminium alone

Fig. 2(b) Effect of rolling temperature on total elongation of 1N90 pure aluminium

(2) Superplastic characteristics of AlN/1N90 Al composite

Superplastic characteristics of AlN₂/1N90 and AlN₃/1N90 Al composites hot-rolled after extrusion is shown in Fig.3. The volume fraction of AlN particle used was $V_f=0.15$. Rolling temperature used was 913 and 923K which is just below liquid temperature of pure aluminium and the testing temperature was 913K. AlN₂/1N90 and AlN₃/1N90 Al composites hot-rolled at 913 and 923K indicate the same m value of 0.3 and the composites hot-rolled at 923K exhibit the total elongation of 150-200% at the strain rate of about 0.1 s^{-1} and at 913K, but the composite hot-rolled at 913K indicate low total elongation less than 100%.

Therefore, rolling at 923K is necessary to avoid crack initiation at an interface during hot rolling in order to produce HSRS for the 1N90 aluminium composites

Figure 3 The relationship between flow stress and strain rate of AlN/1N90 Al composites($V_f=0.15$) hot -rolled after extrusion

(3)Superplastic characteristics of AlN/6061 Al composite

Figure 4(a) shows the relationship between flow stress and strain rate of the AlN3/6061 aluminum alloy composite with $V_f=0.30$ hot-rolled after extrusion. Temperatures of hot rolling used are 673,723 and 818K, and reheating times between rolling passes is 5 minutes. The testing temperatures used are 873K. The flow stress in the composite increases linearly with raising strain rate in the strain rate region from 0.03 up to about 1.5 s^{-1} and the strain rate sensitivity of the composite, m value indicates more than 0.45. The results represent that the predominant deformation mechanism of the AlN2/6061 Al composites is a fine grain boundary sliding in that strain region.

Figure 4(a) Relationship between flow stress and strain rate of AlN3/6061 Al composite with $V_f=0.30$

Total elongations of the AlN3/6061 Al composite hot-rolled after extrusion are shown in Fig.4(b). The AlN3/6061 Al composite hot-rolled at 818K exhibits the total elongation larger than 200% in the strain rate region from 0.1 up to 1.0 S^{-1} and, it is still larger than 300% at the extremely high strain rate of 1.5 S^{-1} . The maximum total elongation becomes more than 500% at the high strain rate of 0.8 s^{-1} and at 873K. But the composite hot-rolled at 673K indicates the same elongation as that in the case of 818K. And the total elongation of the composite pulled at 848K, which is less than solidus line of 6061 matrix becomes about 270% at the strain rate of 0.24 s^{-1} .

Figure 3 (b) Relationship between total elongation and strain rate of AlN3/6061 Al composite with Vf=0.30

(4) Effect of volume fraction of AlN particle

The total elongations of AlN2/6061 and AlN3/6061 Al composites with Vf=0.40 are shown in Fig.5. The AlN3/6061 composites with Vf=0.40 were hot-rolled at 818K after extrusion, although the rolling temperature of the AlN2/6061 Al composite was 903K. The total elongation of the AlN3/6061 Al composite with Vf=0.40 hot-rolled after extrusion becomes about 200-250% in strain rate range from 0.06 up to 1.3 S^{-1} . Therefore, maximum volume fraction of AlN particle in which HSRS can produce probably is 0.40.

Superplastic deformation mechanisms of the ceramic whisker or particulate reinforced aluminium alloy composites should include fine grain boundary sliding, interfacial sliding at a liquid phase(8, 9) and dynamic recrystallization. It is important to make clear, experimentally, how grain boundary sliding could control HSRS, or if interfacial sliding at a liquid phase can occur during HSRS. But how an interfacial sliding could control superplastic deformation at high strain rate during fabrication of a composite is currently under investigation.

Fig.6 indicates fracture surfaces of AlN3/6061 Al composite tested (a) at 848K and (b) at 873K. The appearance of the fracture surfaces of the composites is indicative of a partially melted matrix. These fracture surfaces are consistent

with the fact that both the composites were deformed above or just below the solidus temperature of the 6061 aluminium matrix.

Figure 5 Relationship between total elongation and strain rate of AlN2/6061 and AlN3/6061 Al composites with $V_f=0.40$ hot-rolled after extrusion

A filament in Fig.6 (a) should be connected with a semi-liquid phase near or at the AlN/6061 interface and be built by an interfacial sliding which might happen at a liquid layer at an interface between the matrix and AlN particle. It is, therefore, considered that interfacial sliding at a liquid phase in addition to fine grain boundary sliding should occur during extrusion and hot rolling.

CONCLUSIONS

Thermomechanical processing to produce HSRS for 1N90 pure aluminium, AlN/1N90 and AlN/6061 Al composites fabricated by a P/M method were developed, and the relationship between superplastic characteristics of 1N90 Al and the composite and the thermomechanical processing were investigated. The following results were obtained:

- (1) 1N90 pure aluminium alone hot-rolled above 723K indicates strain rate sensitivity(m value) of 0.45 and the total elongation of 200-300% at 913K and at the strain rate of $0.01s^{-1}$.
- (2) AlN/1N90 Al composites hot-rolled at 923K exhibit the m value of 0.3 and the total elongation of 200% at the strain rate of $0.1 s^{-1}$ and at 913K.
- (3) The composite with $V_f=0.30$ hot-rolled at 673-818K after extrusion exhibits the m value of 0.45 and the total elongation of 300-500% in the strain rate region of $0.08-1.5s^{-1}$ and at 873K.
- (4) Maximum volume fraction of AlN particle to produce HSRS in AlN/6061 Al composite hot-rolled after extrusion was 0.40.
- (5) Fracture surfaces of the composites were covered by a partially melted matrix and filaments observed on fracture surfaces may be evidence that interfacial sliding in a partially melted matrix is an important contribution to HSRS and to hot rolling or extrusion.

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Figure 6 Fracture surfaces of AlN3/6061 Al composite pulled (a) at 848K and (b) at 873K($V_f=0.30$)